

The Effect of Locavorism on Behavior Intention in The Scope of Goal-Directed Behavior Theory: Alaçatı Herb Festival Case of Study

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the effect of locavorism on behavior intention in the context of Goal-Directed Behavior Theory. The research population consists of tourists participating in the Alaçatı Herb Festival in İzmir province, and the survey technique was used to obtain the data by purposive sampling. The questionnaires were collected face-to-face between 24-28 March 2022, and 445 questionnaires were subjected to analysis. The research used Smart PLS statistical software to test the hypotheses for the Goal-Directed Behavior Model, and locavorism scales and the structural equation model were used to analyze the data. In this context, according to the tourists participating in the research, it was determined that only negative anticipated emotions among the variables in the Goal-Directed Behavior Model did not affect desire, and all other variables affected the model. In addition, it was determined that lionization and opposition from the dimensions of the locavorism variable affected behavior, but communalization did not have an effect. Suggestions were developed in line with the results of the study.

Keywords: Goal-Directed Behavior, Locavorism, Tourism, Alaçatı Herb Festival

JEL Code: I23 O32, Z32

1. Introduction

As industrialized countries continue to be dominated by globalized food systems, local food systems play a lesser role. This is mainly due to environmental, economic, and social issues associated with agro-food (Prajapati et al., 2022). For instance, the sector is responsible for 22% of greenhouse gas emissions and 30% of all energy consumed globally, with 79% sourced from fossil fuels (Satterthwaite,

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2008). As a result, food consumption is recognized as a significant sustainability issue, as reflected in the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals, precisely Goal 12, which ensures sustainable consumption and production patterns (Dawes, 2020).

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in consumer demand for sustainable food products and interest in research and politics (Fanzo et al., 2022; Taghikhah et al., 2020). This increase is primarily driven by consumers' increasing concerns about the transparency of their food and their beliefs about the values of local food. These values include health, social, economic, and environmental benefits, and a preference for self-expression through food choices (Ketter, 2019). Nie and Zepeda (2011) identified four lifestyle purchasing patterns for local food: rational consumers who are price-conscious, adventurous consumers who are enthusiastic about local food consumption, careless consumers with the slightest interest in food activities, and the uninvolved conservative group who only seek convenience in food.

Locavorism is a comprehensive perspective that reflects the movement of consumers striving to eat locally sourced foods (Kim and Huang, 2021). Adopting locavorism is shaped by an individual's psychological, cultural, and social perceptions. Research on locavorism has consistently indicated that perceived benefits drive consumers to choose local food and visit local retailers (Conner et al., 2009; Kim and Huang, 2021; Palau-Saumell et al., 2021). Locavorism believes that eating local food helps local farmers, boosts the local economy, and protects the environment (Choi et al., 2021). Moreover, although these perceived benefits are not absolute, they perceive local food as healthier than food that travels long distances and is more reliable in times of political crisis (Kim and Huang, 2021).

The concept of locavorism can be understood through the theory of goal-directed behavior. This theory suggests that individuals' actions are guided by their goals and their intentions to achieve those goals. In the case of locavorism, the goal is to consume locally sourced food, and the intention is to enjoy the perceived benefits associated with this choice (Ertz, 2016; Kim and Huang, 2021).

GDB is a theoretical framework that helps explain why people engage in certain behaviors by considering their goals and the factors influencing them (Su et al., 2022). According to this model, human behavior is directed toward achieving goals, and these goals are influenced by attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control (Ajzen and Madden, 1986). The GDB provides valuable insights into understanding how consumer behavior is influenced by beliefs, attitudes, and social norms, which are central to the locavorism movement. Numerous studies on locavorism have consistently shown that perceived benefits strongly influence consumers' decisions to choose local food (Desrochers, 2016) and support local businesses such as regional specialty lodging (RSL) (Lang and Lemmerer, 2019).

For example, locavores believe that eating local food helps local farmers, boosts local economies, and helps protect the environment (Desrochers, 2016).

A compelling case study of locavorism and its impact on behavioral intentions can be observed in İzmir, Turkey. İzmir has a rich agricultural heritage, and its residents have a solid connection to the land and the food it produces. However, like many other cities, İzmir has experienced a rapid increase in the presence of multinational food companies and chain restaurants, which has led to the decline of local food systems. To address this gap in the literature, this study aims to investigate the effect of locavorism on the behavioral intention of tourists attending the Alaçatı Herb Festival in İzmir province.

2. Theoretical Framework and Development of Hypotheses

Goal-Directed Behavior Theory

The development of theories and models of human behavior can be traced back to the early days of social psychology. As early as 1862, psychologists worked on theories emphasizing how attitudes could significantly influence behavior. This research led to many new theories between 1918 and 1925. Desire plays a crucial role in shaping human behavior because it reflects a person's mind and emotions related to achieving their goals or obtaining a particular object (Taylor et al., 2005).

An essential factor that drives behavior is behavioral intention. Behavioral intention reveals a person's willingness and plan to engage in a particular behavior (Perugini and Bagozzi, 2001). In other words, for a particular behavior to occur, the individual must first form the intention to perform it. This intention represents a commitment and effort the person makes to perform the behavior (Ajzen, 1991). The result of behavior stems from the formation of an intention. In this sense, intention can be defined as the outcome of a previous decision (Bagozzi, 1992). Behavior intention refers to an individual's attempt to perform a behavior better than their current or actual behavior to achieve satisfaction (Ajzen, 1985: 30). People's past experiences influence their behavior. Behavior intention is the initial step (Timothy et al., 2007) of a behavior or an individual's reaction to a particular situation (Han and Ryu, 2007). A robust behavior intention increases the likelihood of performing the behavior (Frey and George, 2010). It positively or negatively impacts an individual's thoughts (Korol and Bevelander, 2022). Behavior intention, viewed as an indicator of an individual's desire and efforts to act (Armitage and Conner, 2001), also explains the planned actions following service use (Bidin and Shamsudin, 2013). GDB is an alternative perspective to the Rational Action Theory (RET) and the Planned Behavior Theory (PDT) that was developed to understand and explain the psychological processes related to consumers making decisions toward a goal or behavior (Han and Ryu, 2012; Ruan et al., 2020).

Intent and desire are considered the first factor in decision-making in GDB. Evidence has been shown of the role of intent in forming intentions and its role as a mediator in proposed relationships between theoretical variables and its function as a function of these variables (Bagozzi and Dholakia, 2006; Perugini and Bagozzi,

2001; Poels and Dewitte, 2008). Secondly, anticipated positive and negative feelings are included in GDB. Perugini and Bagozzi (2001) argue that these feelings emerge in evaluating the outcomes of reaching a specific goal. Empirical studies have revealed that positive and negative expected emotions contribute to the production or reduction of a particular behavior execution desire in the decision-making process (Bagozzi and Dholakia, 2006; Lee et al., 2012; Perugini and Bagozzi, 2001; Poels and Dewitte, 2008; Taylor et al., 2009). GDB incorporates past behavior to predict future human behavior. Past behavior is believed to play an essential role in human decision-making (Perugini and Bagozzi, 2001; Ouellette and Wood, 1998).

Attitude refers to evaluating a goal or behavior in terms of its positive or negative attributes. It is a psychological state that motivates or discourages behavior (Ajzen, 1991; Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975). Attitudes can be shaped by personal experience or social influence (Perugini and Bagozzi, 2001). In the context of GDB, attitudes are considered crucial in decision-making because they can influence the formation of behavioral intentions and actual behavior (Ajzen, 1991; Perugini and Bagozzi, 2001).

H₁: Attitude has a significant positive effect on desire.

Subjective norms refer to the perceived expectations of others regarding a goal or behavior. They play an important role in shaping human behavior, as individuals often conform to the expectations of their social group. In GDB, subjective norms are considered essential in decision-making because they can influence the formation of behavioral intentions and actual behavior (Perugini and Bagozzi, 2001).

H₂: Subjective norm has a significant positive effect on desire.

Positive anticipated emotions refer to the positive feelings an individual expects to experience due to their behavior, such as happiness, excitement, satisfaction, and fulfillment (Pérez-Villarreal et al., 2019). These emotions play an important role in motivation and goal-directed behavior by motivating individuals to pursue their goals. When people anticipate positive emotions, they are more likely to engage in goal-directed behavior because they expect a positive outcome (Leone et al., 2005).

H₃: Positive anticipated emotions have a significant positive effect on desire.

On the other hand, negative anticipated emotions refer to the negative feelings an individual expects to experience due to their behavior, such as fear, anxiety, frustration, and disappointment (Odou and Schill, 2020). Negative anticipated emotions can dampen motivation and goal-directed behavior by

discouraging individuals from pursuing their goals. People who anticipate negative emotions are less likely to engage in goal-directed behavior because they expect an unfavorable outcome (Wang, 2011).

H₄: Negative anticipated emotions have a significant positive effect on desire.

Desire is central to GDB, driving individuals to set and pursue their goals. The desired outcome becomes the focus of an individual's efforts, fueled by desire (de Wit and Dickinson, 2009). The level of desire for the desired outcome determines its salience to the individual, which in turn influences their motivation to pursue the goal (Fry et al., 2014). Understanding the relationship between desire and goal-directed behavior is critical to explaining why people act the way they do and how they can achieve their desired outcomes. GDB is a psychological theory that attempts to shed light on this relationship and provides a framework for understanding how desire drives motivation and goal-directed behavior (Choi and Park, 2017).

H₅: Desire has a significant positive effect on intentions.

Intentions are a critical component of the GDB model and are crucial in shaping our goal-directed actions. Intention refers to an individual's deliberate and conscious decision to engage in a particular behavior to achieve a desired outcome (Netemeyer et al., 1991; Perugini and Bagozzi, 2001). People with a solid intention to engage in a behavior are more likely to follow through and perform the behavior because they are motivated by their desire to achieve the desired outcome. A solid intention can also increase an individual's belief in their ability to perform the behavior, further increasing their motivation to act (Esposito et al., 2016).

H₆: Intentions have a significant positive effect on behavior.

Behavior refers to individuals' actions to achieve their desired outcome (Aarts and Dijksterhuis, 2000; Moors et al., 2017). GDB is driven by the anticipation of positive and negative emotions, the frequency of past behavior, and individuals' perceptions of their ability to perform the behavior (Song et al., 2017). When individuals anticipate positive emotions, they are more likely to engage in goal-directed behavior, whereas anticipated negative emotions can serve as a deterrent (Bagozzi et al., 2003).

Perceived behavioral control refers to an individual's perception of his or her ability to control a goal or behavior (Perugini and Bagozzi, 2001; Odou and Schill, 2020). Believing that one has control over a goal or behavior can increase the likelihood of pursuing that goal or behavior (Ajzen, 1991; Perugini and Bagozzi, 2001). In GDB, perceived behavioral control is essential for decision-making because it can influence the formation of behavioral intentions. The frequency of past behavior indicates that the behavior has been practiced for more than six

months, whereas novelty refers to something that has occurred in the past month or less (Leone et al., 2004).

H₇: Perceived behavioral control has a significant positive effect on craving.

H₈: Perceived behavioral control has a significantly positive effect on behavior.

Past behavior frequency refers to the number of times an individual has performed a particular behavior. This aspect of GDB is crucial because it can influence future behavior by shaping an individual's expectations and beliefs about their ability to perform the behavior (Danner et al., 2008). When individuals have frequently engaged in behavior and experienced positive outcomes, they are likelier to engage in goal-directed behavior.

H₉: Frequency of past behavior has a significant positive effect on desire.

H₁₀: Frequency of past behavior has a significant positive effect on intentions.

H₁₁: Frequency of past behavior significantly positively affects behavior.

Locavorism

Locavorism is a relatively new term that emerged in the first decade of the 21st century. The term "locavore" was first coined by Prentice (2006) in his book *Full Moon Feast* and defined as "a movement in which people seek to eat locally sourced food" (Fitzgerald, 2016: 2). While locavorism is often reduced to eating food from a specific radius, it refers to the adoption of a "mindset about shared commitments to various forms of environmental sustainability, community revitalization, human health, and animal welfare" (Rudy, 2012: 28). Locavorism is seen by Fitzgerald (2016) as a humanist form of activism as it encourages people to consume conscious food. Locavores aim to change consumer culture and ideology and can thus be regarded as a new consumer ideology due to shared beliefs (Choi et al., 2021; Reich et al., 2018). In addition, the fact that only when consumers subscribe to a view do they take meaningful actions, such as food product choices and purchases, as well as the seldom return to nonlocal food after the locavore idea has been established in consumers' minds, points to locavorism being a solid consumer ideology (Kim and Huang, 2021).

Reich et al. (2018) developed a tripartite framework to foster a better understanding of locavorism. They identified three core locavorism components: lionization, opposition, and communication. Lionization is inspired by the lion's characteristics, superiority, and credibility and refers to locavores believing that local food is of superior quality, taste, and nutrition than nonlocal food (Jekanowski et al., 2000). Opposition pertains to the underlying criticism of mainstream food systems and all nonlocal corporations (Zhang et al., 2020). The third dimension,

communication, relates to the support of local communities (Reich et al., 2018). It assumes that local food consumption creates economic benefits and strengthens social bonds, leading to stronger communities. These three core elements of locavorism are reciprocal (Haedicke, 2015). The framework suggests that, as opposed to prior research, which sees the ideology as a reason for food preferences, the preference for local food is an ideology (Reich et al., 2018).

Again, it must be emphasized that while locavorism encourages local food consumption, it does not advocate the complete abolishment of food transport. It simply incites an increased intake of locally sourced items, wherever possible, to decrease dependence on a mainstream food system (Fitzgerald, 2016). Furthermore, locavorism is often labeled an elitist movement. Locally sourced items cost around ten percent more than their nonlocal counterparts (Rudy, 2012). They are harder to access because they are limited in most farmers' markets, high-end stores, and other agricultural sales points.

At the outset, the reasons for local food product choice are manifold. Scholars propose they range from demographic factors, information seeking and knowledge, context, and behavior attitudes, as a thorough literature review by Feldmann and Hamm (2015) suggests. This is supported by several studies that identified environmental attitudes, health consciousness, and community attachment as the three main psychosocial factors positively predicting locavorism (Choi et al., 2021; Kumar and Smith, 2018). Palau-Saumell et al. (2021) conducted a study to determine the impact of the COVID-19 outbreak on locavorism (food consumption) produced locally. They found that locavorism has a positive effect on behavioral intention. Kim and Huang (2021) examined the impact of locavorism on behavioral intention by determining its factors. As a result, it was a strong predictor of behavioral intention. Choi et al. (2021) examined consumers' local food ideology, called 'locavorism,' as an intermediate process explaining the effects of three psychosocial factors from the new consumer movement theory on consumers' behavioral intentions. Environmental attitude, community commitment, and health awareness were positively related to locavorism. Zhang et al. (2022), in their study to determine the effects of locavorism on the behavioral intention of individuals in China, locavorism consumption of locally produced locavorism food was found to have a positive impact on behavioral intention.

H₁₂: Lionization has a significant positive effect on behavior.

H₁₃: Opposition has a significant positive effect on behavior.

H₁₄: Communalization has a significant positive effect on behavior.

Figure 1. Research model proposal

3. Methodology

Study site: Alaçatı Herb Festival

The Izmir Alaçatı Herb Festival is a highly anticipated annual event held in the enchanting coastal city of İzmir, Turkey. This vibrant festival exuberantly celebrates the city's deep-rooted cultural heritage and thriving local food scene, making it an unforgettable experience for all participants. From age-old traditional dishes to innovative fusion cuisine, the festival promises to tantalize the taste buds of every food lover.

Central to the appeal of the Izmir Alaçatı Herb Festival is the exquisite local cuisine that showcases a delightful blend of Turkish and Mediterranean influences. Visitors are treated to a delectable array of dishes, including succulent kebabs, tempting meze platters, and the freshest seafood from the sea. The flavors are a testament to the city's culinary diversity and leave a lasting impression on all who partake in the feast.

However, the festival is not only about gastronomic delights; it also serves as a gateway to explore the fascinating facets of Izmir's rich cultural heritage. Amid the festivities, participants will have the opportunity to delve into the city's storied past by visiting historical buildings and monuments that are living testimonies of the city's past. A stroll through local markets and shops offers a chance to immerse oneself in the vibrant tapestry of everyday life. At the same time, cultural performances and events provide a glimpse into the soul of the city's artistic expression.

Research Instrument

The survey questionnaire consists of three coalitions. The first coalition retains categorical inquiries to describe the participants' demographic characteristics. The Theory of GDB Scale developed by Perugini and Bagozzi (2001) was used in the second part of the questionnaire. The theory of goal-directed behavior variables consists of attitudes (7), subjective norm (5), positive anticipated emotions (5), negative anticipated emotions (5), perceived behavior control (4), desire (4), intentions (3), behavior (4), frequency past behavior (2). In the third part, the statements belonging to the sub-factors of the locavorism scale are included. Lionization (3 items), opposition (4 items) and communalization (4 items) sub-factors were adapted from the study of Reich, Beck and Price (2018). It was evaluated under the supervision of three experts and academicians to validate and improve this measurement tool to ensure that the questionnaire items were adequate in terms of clarity, relevance, and consistency. After the evaluation, some scale items were removed to redefine the items in the questionnaire and increase their comprehensibility. Responses were estimated using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from "strongly disagree (1)" to "strongly agree (5)".

Sampling and Data Collection

This study aimed to determine the effect of locavorism on behavior intention within the scope of GDB Theory. Since it is difficult to reach the entire universe, sampling was used. In the research, the purposeful sampling technique, one of the non-probabilistic sampling methods, was preferred. The study was conducted between 24-28 March 2022, and 480 surveys were distributed to participants. The G*POWER 3.1 software was employed to determine the sample size needed to achieve the desired level of statistical power. The analysis results indicated that the smallest sample size that would provide sufficient energy would be 200 participants. The sample size was determined using Power = 0.80, $f^2 = 0.15$, and $\alpha = 0.05$. After the surveys were distributed, 445 were deemed suitable for analysis. The participants were provided with information about the research objectives to ensure their responses were accurate and aligned with the study's aims. The data was analyzed to determine the average conditions, and the results were used to conclude the studied subject.

The objective of this study was not to generalize the results to the universe but to examine the average conditions to obtain information on the subject. The study was based on the principles laid out by Yıldırım and Şimşek (2005), who emphasize the importance of understanding the average conditions in research. The Mahalanobis distance for outliers was determined using the Mahalanobis distance. No outliers were found (Mahalanobis D (17) 58.9, $p < 0.001$) (De Maesschalck et al., 2000). Finally, the assumption of normal distribution was checked using skewness and kurtosis values. Since the skewness values are between 1.00 and 0.09 and kurtosis values are between 0.7 and 0.7, the data are normally distributed

(Kline, 2011). After the data screening process, the external and internal models were analyzed.

Data Analyzed

The information gathered for analysis underwent a sophisticated three-step approach for evaluation utilizing the Smart PLS statistics software. The data was initially coded using the SPSS statistics software (Hair et al., 2014) before undergoing measurement model analysis to assess the validity and reliability of the scales. Next, the structural model analysis was performed, which uncovered demographic insights along with the results of truth and reliability analysis, discriminant validity analysis (Fornell-Larcker criterion, HTMT, Cross-loadings), model fit goodness values model effect size, and structural equation model results, presented in tabulated format.

The collinearity test proposed by Kock and Lynn (2012) was performed to identify constructs with outer variance factor (VIF) values equal to or higher than 5. According to the relevant results, it was determined that there were no collinearity problems in the outer VIF value of all constructs, and the values were less than 5 (Hair et al., 2017).

Confirmatory tetrad analyses (CTA) were performed on the scales belonging to the model (Gudergan et al., 2008), and it was determined that all of the variables had a value of "0" in the confidence intervals and showed the reflective feature (Hair et al., 2021). The CTA analysis examined adjusted confidence intervals calculated with Bonferroni correction. All scales were found to be reflective.

In the literature (Anwar et al., 2022; Schaarschmidt et al., 2015; Soto-Acosta et al., 2007), there is the idea that questionnaires used from a single source potentially pose a bias threat in social science research. Therefore, we assessed whether common method bias threatens the interpretation of research results. All items were subjected to principal components factor analysis, and Harman's one-factor test was applied (Fuller et al., 2016; Podsakoff and Organ, 1986). It was determined that all items entered did not explain the 50% variance threshold with a single factor (36%), and the study had no common method bias.

4. Findings

Measurement Model Analysis

53.1% of the participants are female, and 46.9% are male, and when marital status is analyzed, 55% are married, and 45% are single. When the age ranges of the participants are analyzed, it is seen that the highest participation is from the 36-

45 age range with 31.8%, and this rate is followed by the 26-35 age range with 25.1%. When the participants' education levels are analyzed, 53.1% are undergraduates, and 1% are PhD graduates. When the income status of the participants is analyzed, 39.6% have medium income, while 2.7% have a high income.

Cronbach Alpha (α) and rho_A values were examined for the scale's reliability. Chin (1998) and Dijkstra and Henseler (2015) state that α and rho_A values greater than 0.70 are reliable. In addition, the rho_A reliability coefficient gave better results than α values. AVE values were examined for the convergent validity of the scale and integrated reliability (rho_C) values for internal consistency. According to Fornell and Larcker (1981), AVE should be >0.50 and above, and according to Bagozzi and Yi (1988), rho_C should be >0.60 and above (see Table 1). All variables were found to be above the threshold.

Table 1. The Results of validity and reliability analyses for the variables

Items	λ	α	rho_A	rho_C	AVE
Goal-Directed Behaviors					
Attitudes (A)					
<i>Participating in the Herb Festival...</i>					
They think it is positive behavior.	0.884	0.955	0.956	0.963	0.787
They think it is a worthwhile behavior.	0.927				
They think it is healthy behavior.	0.799				
They think it is an appealing behavior.	0.875				
They think it is acceptable behavior.	0.912				
They think it is required behavior.	0.907				
They think it is supportive behavior.	0.900				
Subjective Norm (S.N.)					
<i>The people I care about, the Herb Festival...</i>					
They think that I should participate.	0.640	0.856	0.862	0.898	0.641
They think it is suitable to participate.	0.797				
They understand if I participate.	0.862				
They encourage me to participate.	0.836				
They encourage me to participate.	0.848				
Positive Anticipated Emotions (PAE)					
<i>If I attend the Herb Festival in the future again...</i>					
I am excited about it.	0.965	0.961	0.964	0.972	0.873
Happy about it.	0.979				
Confident about it.	0.974				
I am feeling happy about it.	0.976				
I am feeling proud of it.	0.760				
Negative Anticipated Emotions (NAE)					
<i>If I cannot attend the Herb Festival again in the future...</i>					
It makes me feel uncomfortable.	0.804	0.880	0.900	0.912	0.674
Make me feel angry.	0.768				
I am frustrated and disappointed.	0.848				
Make me feel sad and guilty.	0.875				

I am feeling unhappy and anxious.	0.807				
Perceived Behavior Control (PBC)					
<i>The Herb Festival...</i>					
Should I want to, I am sure I can see the region.	0.779	0.831	0.835	0.887	0.663
I could retake part.	0.840				
There is enough money to retake part.	0.836				
There is enough time to retake the part.	0.802				
Desire (D)					
<i>Soon, the Herb Festival...</i>					
Eager to region.	0.783	0.828	0.828	0.886	0.660
Eager to participate again.	0.841				
Hopefully, I would like to participate again.	0.788				
I want to participate again.	0.837				
Intentions (I)					
<i>Soon, the Herb Festival...</i>					
We are planning on attending again.	0.810	0.710	0.718	0.835	0.629
Intend to participate again.	0.796				
I will spend time and money to participate again.	0.773				
Behavior (B)					
<i>Soon, the Herb Festival...</i>					
I will endeavor to region.	0.883	0.887	0.887	0.922	0.747
We are prepared to participate again.	0.851				
Will recommend	0.892				
Will buy local products again	0.829				
Frequency Past Behavior (FPB)					
<i>Herb Festival in the past...</i>					
Often, I participated.	0.799	0.562	0.574	0.819	0.694
Often bought local products.	0.865				
LOCAVORISM					
Lionization (L)					
Locally produced foods taste better.	0.864	0.836	0.836	0.902	0.753
All else equal, there is a taste difference between a locally produced food and one that was shipped from somewhere else	0.859				
Locally produced foods are more nutritious than foods that have been shipped from somewhere else.	0.880				
Opposition (O)					
I do not trust foods produced by large multinational corporations.	0.852	0.850	0.851	0.899	0.690
Large, global food systems are destined to fail.	0.766				
I would go out of my way to avoid buying food from a large retail grocery chain.	0.855				
I feel comfortable eating something if I know exactly where it was produced.	0.848				
Communalization (C)					
Buying locally produced foods supports sustainable farming practices.	0.839	0.804	0.875	0.866	0.618
Buying local foods helps build a more prosperous community.	0.784				
I like to support local farmers whenever possible.	0.735				
Supporting the local food economy is important to me.	0.784				

*Measured using a 5-point Likert scale format (1=strongly disagree, 3=decided, 5=strongly agree), λ = Outer Loadings, α =Cronbach Alpha, ρ_A and ρ_C = Composite reliability, AVE= Average variance explained

Source: Authors' calculations

To determine the discriminant validity of the scales, the Fornell Larcker criterion was calculated. When the correlation loads between the variables were examined, it was determined that all variables were lower than $\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$ value and thus provided the first stage of discriminant validity (Fornell and Larcker, 1981) (See Table 2).

Table 2. Results of Fornell Larcker criterion and HTMT ratio

Fornell-Larcker Criterion												
	AT	B	C	D	FPB	I	L	NAE	O	PAE	PBC	SN
AT	0.887											
B	0.181	0.864										
C	0.119	0.183	0.786									
D	0.400	0.444	0.174	0.813								
FPB	0.102	0.482	0.136	0.177	0.833							
I	0.193	0.418	0.151	0.263	0.291	0.793						
L	0.197	0.504	0.099	0.138	0.452	0.348	0.868					
NAE	0.201	0.316	0.034	0.299	0.109	0.192	0.265	0.821				
O	0.198	0.445	0.184	0.259	0.567	0.276	0.347	0.125	0.831			
PAE	0.344	0.222	0.113	0.326	0.077	0.275	0.094	0.349	0.142	0.935		
PBC	0.177	0.251	0.116	0.437	0.077	0.161	0.134	0.221	0.131	0.105	0.814	
SN	0.293	0.190	0.095	0.335	0.067	0.095	0.160	0.368	0.172	0.188	0.244	0.801

HTMT Ration												
AT												
B	0.197											
C	0.129	0.198										
D	0.448	0.518	0.208									
FPB	0.142	0.679	0.185	0.253								
I	0.224	0.505	0.188	0.335	0.465							
L	0.221	0.585	0.111	0.166	0.658	0.451						
NAE	0.224	0.358	0.069	0.343	0.152	0.249	0.315					
O	0.219	0.511	0.217	0.308	0.801	0.356	0.411	0.143				
PAE	0.360	0.242	0.122	0.365	0.103	0.319	0.105	0.379	0.159			
PBC	0.198	0.293	0.145	0.525	0.120	0.198	0.162	0.254	0.153	0.117		
SN	0.322	0.217	0.103	0.395	0.110	0.117	0.186	0.424	0.202	0.208	0.290	

Attitudes (A); Subjective Norm (SN); Positive Anticipated Emotions (PAE); Negative Anticipated Emotions (NAE); Perceived Behavior Control (PBC); Desire (D); Intentions (I); Behavior (B); Frequency Past Behavior (FPB); Lionization (L); Opposition (O); Communalization (C)

Source: Authors' calculations

When the HTMT discriminant validity analysis of the scales was examined, it was stated that each value should be below 0.9 (Voorhees et al., 2016). When the relevant analysis results were discussed, it was determined that the correlation value averages of the variables were below 0.9, and the second stage of discriminant validity was provided (See Table 2).

Cross-loading values and measurement items of each construct were examined in the study. The correlation loadings between the items of each scale are expected to be higher than the correlation loadings of other items (Hair et al., 2011). It is argued that the cross-loading value of the relevant items should be greater than 0.7 (Ghozali and Latan, 2015). It was determined that the cross-loading values of the research were more significant than 0.7, and the last stage of discriminant validity was achieved (see Table 3).

Table 3. Discriminant validity cross-loading values

	AT	B	C	D	FPB	I	L	NAE	O	PAE	PBC	SN
At1	0.884	0.145	0.141	0.360	0.077	0.186	0.140	0.176	0.179	0.344	0.169	0.288
At2	0.927	0.170	0.146	0.363	0.080	0.213	0.160	0.191	0.171	0.333	0.183	0.244
At3	0.799	0.151	0.130	0.377	0.111	0.157	0.148	0.172	0.161	0.231	0.202	0.190
At4	0.875	0.162	0.062	0.305	0.085	0.150	0.224	0.224	0.163	0.303	0.157	0.260
At5	0.912	0.109	0.113	0.340	0.039	0.152	0.114	0.117	0.159	0.290	0.118	0.269
At6	0.907	0.192	0.090	0.365	0.144	0.163	0.245	0.204	0.217	0.301	0.134	0.288
At7	0.900	0.192	0.045	0.361	0.091	0.171	0.198	0.169	0.179	0.335	0.130	0.281
B1	0.090	0.883	0.112	0.362	0.430	0.375	0.463	0.246	0.421	0.176	0.189	0.136
B2	0.173	0.851	0.161	0.423	0.460	0.378	0.356	0.259	0.414	0.161	0.209	0.185
B3	0.199	0.892	0.166	0.405	0.396	0.328	0.471	0.263	0.373	0.214	0.201	0.148
B4	0.168	0.829	0.195	0.346	0.380	0.363	0.451	0.328	0.327	0.218	0.270	0.190
C1	0.110	0.200	0.839	0.151	0.166	0.119	0.127	0.053	0.207	0.110	0.075	0.118
C2	0.080	0.120	0.784	0.156	0.059	0.145	0.017	-0.039	0.123	0.050	0.115	0.070
C3	0.083	0.085	0.735	0.109	0.140	0.091	0.072	0.009	0.152	0.064	0.085	0.040
C4	0.090	0.125	0.784	0.125	0.044	0.120	0.066	0.060	0.070	0.115	0.103	0.039
D1	0.342	0.348	0.129	0.783	0.112	0.140	0.066	0.215	0.192	0.301	0.431	0.236
D2	0.332	0.308	0.148	0.841	0.175	0.199	0.119	0.267	0.233	0.261	0.326	0.275
D3	0.323	0.422	0.164	0.788	0.137	0.300	0.127	0.218	0.189	0.275	0.346	0.249
D4	0.302	0.364	0.126	0.837	0.151	0.214	0.137	0.273	0.228	0.222	0.315	0.329
Fpb1	0.025	0.369	0.061	0.098	0.799	0.233	0.358	0.067	0.332	0.035	0.065	-0.011
Fpb2	0.135	0.432	0.158	0.190	0.865	0.252	0.394	0.111	0.592	0.089	0.063	0.112
I1	0.111	0.272	0.066	0.148	0.219	0.810	0.300	0.209	0.189	0.182	0.090	0.072
I2	0.201	0.450	0.153	0.231	0.194	0.796	0.279	0.142	0.191	0.287	0.193	0.074
I3	0.129	0.236	0.126	0.234	0.287	0.773	0.251	0.113	0.279	0.163	0.078	0.079
L1	0.123	0.437	0.029	0.135	0.374	0.281	0.864	0.255	0.251	0.062	0.147	0.110
L2	0.203	0.434	0.164	0.109	0.446	0.362	0.859	0.209	0.343	0.091	0.099	0.147
L3	0.188	0.440	0.066	0.115	0.357	0.263	0.880	0.227	0.309	0.091	0.102	0.158
Nae1	0.179	0.285	-0.002	0.208	0.113	0.148	0.196	0.804	0.113	0.343	0.109	0.305
Nae2	0.195	0.213	0.027	0.223	0.053	0.151	0.228	0.768	0.098	0.292	0.160	0.308
Nae3	0.201	0.256	0.042	0.212	0.101	0.201	0.275	0.848	0.107	0.290	0.175	0.347
Nae4	0.158	0.288	0.010	0.316	0.105	0.151	0.185	0.875	0.127	0.343	0.218	0.294
Nae5	0.108	0.253	0.064	0.242	0.074	0.145	0.224	0.807	0.066	0.164	0.224	0.273
O1	0.138	0.353	0.197	0.204	0.480	0.250	0.248	0.067	0.852	0.127	0.099	0.143
O2	0.132	0.368	0.167	0.149	0.448	0.224	0.341	0.146	0.766	0.112	0.089	0.074
O3	0.179	0.389	0.158	0.260	0.488	0.208	0.266	0.117	0.855	0.110	0.113	0.156
O4	0.208	0.365	0.092	0.244	0.466	0.235	0.297	0.083	0.848	0.125	0.132	0.197
Pae1	0.328	0.206	0.095	0.325	0.039	0.287	0.091	0.340	0.116	0.965	0.104	0.189
Pae2	0.335	0.205	0.096	0.314	0.062	0.292	0.089	0.344	0.117	0.979	0.084	0.150
Pae3	0.329	0.219	0.079	0.294	0.073	0.265	0.094	0.340	0.133	0.974	0.082	0.170
Pae4	0.342	0.213	0.091	0.298	0.056	0.278	0.096	0.342	0.114	0.976	0.086	0.162
Pae5	0.269	0.193	0.170	0.288	0.136	0.153	0.067	0.259	0.188	0.760	0.137	0.207
Pbc1	0.164	0.180	0.059	0.328	-0.003	0.138	0.099	0.168	0.060	0.084	0.779	0.177
Pbc2	0.172	0.211	0.106	0.399	0.149	0.119	0.059	0.153	0.133	0.120	0.840	0.175
Pbc3	0.137	0.256	0.111	0.317	0.064	0.167	0.138	0.205	0.131	0.037	0.836	0.211
Pbc4	0.103	0.170	0.099	0.376	0.027	0.102	0.144	0.196	0.096	0.098	0.802	0.232
Sn1	0.235	0.163	0.019	0.247	0.060	0.038	0.154	0.237	0.090	0.131	0.157	0.640
Sn2	0.271	0.199	0.124	0.288	0.076	0.085	0.194	0.320	0.172	0.127	0.223	0.797
Sn3	0.198	0.123	0.080	0.248	0.048	0.061	0.086	0.261	0.152	0.136	0.213	0.862
Sn4	0.253	0.144	0.065	0.301	0.027	0.116	0.118	0.345	0.116	0.183	0.165	0.836
Sn5	0.201	0.123	0.086	0.243	0.057	0.066	0.075	0.290	0.156	0.170	0.215	0.848

Attitudes (A); Subjective Norm (SN); Positive Anticipated Emotions (PAE); Negative Anticipated Emotions (NAE); Perceived Behaviour Control (PBC); Desire (D); Intentions (I); Behaviour (B); Frequency Past Behaviour (FPB); Lionization (L); Opposition (O); Communalization (C)

Source: Authors' calculations

Table 4. Discriminant validity cross-loading values

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model	Critical Value	References
SRMR	0.050	0.061	0.08	Hu and Bentler, 1998
d_ULS	3.250	4.740	0.05	Henseler et al., 2016
d_G	1.652	1.713	0.05	
X ²	3.823.084	3.900.229	-	Dijkstra and Henseler, 2015
NFI	0.785	0.781	0.80	Lohmöller, 1989
GoF	0.467		0.36	Tenenhaus et al., 2005

Source: Authors' calculations

The goodness of fit values of the model was tested before testing the research model. Standard Root Mean Square Root (SRMR) is the difference between the observed and observed correlation, and the relevant value should be less than 0.08 (Hu and Bentler, 1998). The other fit index is the Normed Fit Index (NFI), an appropriate incremental measure calculated and compared with the X² value of the proposed model. NFI values above 0.9 represent an acceptable fit (Lohmöller, 1989). Dijkstra and Henseler (2015) suggest that d_ULS (Euclidean distance) and d_G (Geodesic distance) should be examined as two different ways to calculate this discrepancy. Suppose the difference between the correlation matrix implied by the tested model and the empirical correlation matrix is so tiny that it can only be attributed to sampling error. In that case, it is a good model ($p > 0.05$). Henseler et al. (2016) stated that d_ULS and d_G should be lower than <95% bootstrapped quantile value. The GoF (Goodness of fit) value is the result of the square root of the product of the AVE mean and R² means and is used to determine the general predictive power of the research model (Tenenhaus et al., 2005). When the goodness of fit values of the model are analyzed, it can be said that all values provide a good fit (see Table 4).

Structural Model Analysis

The research model's linearity path coefficients (R²) and effect size (f^2) values were calculated. To evaluate the significance of PLS path coefficients, t values were calculated by taking 5000 sub-samples with bootstrapping. When the VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) values were examined during the structural equation modelling process of the research model, it was understood that the relevant matters were below 5, and there was no linearity problem (Hair et al., 2021). It is seen that the effect size coefficients (f^2) are between 0.006 and 0.153. When the R² values obtained from the model were examined, it was found that behaviour was explained by 4.3%, desire by 3.7% and intention by 1.3% (see Table 5).

Mean Absolute Error (MAE) (PLSPredict) was analyzed to examine the mean magnitude of error related to the results of endogenous variables and to reveal the differences between them. When PLS-MAE and LV-MAE values of the dependent variables are compared, it is determined that LV-MAE values have a

higher ratio than PLS-MAE values. In addition, on the other hand, it was determined that PLS and LV Q^2 predicted values were higher than 0. In this direction, it was determined that the model's predictive power was high (Hair et al., 2021).

Table 5. Result of structural model analysis

	InnerVIF			f^2			R ²	Q ²
	B	D	I	B	D	I		
B							0.427	0.308
D			1.032				0.366	0.233
FPB	1.670	1.021	1.032	0.041	0.016	0.071		
C	1.055			0.005				
I	1.207			0.054			0.131	0.075
L	1.361			0.092				
O	1.544			0.028				
PBC	1.048	1.099		0.034	0.153			
NAE		1.306			0.006			
PAE		1.251			0.032			
SN		1.257			0.020			
AT		1.226			0.066			
CVPAT								
	B	D	I	Overall				
Average loss difference	-0.289	-0.318	-0.116	-0.252				
t value	4098	6229	3132	5797				
p-value	0.000	0.000	0.002	0.000				

Attitudes (A); Subjective Norm (SN); Positive Anticipated Emotions (PAE); Negative Anticipated Emotions (NAE); Perceived Behaviour Control (PBC); Desire (D); Intentions (I); Behaviour (B); Frequency Past Behaviour (FPB); Lionization (L); Opposition (O); Communalization (C)

Source: Authors' calculations

Table 6. Results of the structural equation model

	Hypotheses	β	\bar{X}	S.D	t	p	R
H ₁	A -> D	0.227	0.228	0.046	4.936	0.000***	√
H ₂	SN -> D	0.127	0.131	0.048	2.663	0.008*	√
H ₃	PAE -> D	0.159	0.158	0.042	3.773	0.000***	√
H ₄	NAE -> D	0.067	0.067	0.048	1.404	0.161	X
H ₅	D -> I	0.219	0.221	0.050	4.420	0.000***	√
H ₆	I -> B	0.195	0.193	0.046	4.195	0.000***	√
H ₇	PBC -> D	0.328	0.326	0.048	6.855	0.000***	√
H ₈	PBC -> B	0.142	0.139	0.044	3.244	0.001**	√
H ₉	FPB -> D	0.100	0.102	0.037	2.695	0.007*	√
H ₁₀	FPB -> I	0.252	0.260	0.057	4.423	0.000***	√
H ₁₁	FPB -> B	0.196	0.200	0.056	3.489	0.001**	√
H ₁₂	L -> B	0.269	0.262	0.051	5.256	0.000***	√
H ₁₃	O -> B	0.158	0.158	0.056	2.802	0.005*	√
H ₁₄	C -> B	0.054	0.064	0.036	1.503	0.134	X

Attitudes (A); Subjective Norm (SN); Positive Anticipated Emotions (PAE); Negative Anticipated Emotions (NAE); Perceived Behaviour Control (PBC); Desire (D); Intentions (I); Behaviour (B); Frequency Past Behaviour (FPB); Lionization (L); Opposition (O); Communalization (C)

β = Beta, \bar{X} =Arithmetic Mean, S.D=Standard Deviation, t=statistic value, p=significance value, R=Result, p<0,05*, p<0,001**, p<0,000***

Source: Authors' calculations

Developed by Liengard et al. (2021), CVPAT was designed to provide a solution for prediction-oriented model comparison in PLS-SEM. The CVPAT assesses the predictive ability of PLS-SEM models by testing whether their average loss value is significantly lower than the average loss values of the two benchmark models. A negative difference in the average loss values indicates that PLS-SEM models have better predictive capabilities than benchmark models. Hence, for the CVPAT to substantiate the superiority of PLS-SEM models, the difference in the average loss values should be significantly below zero (Hair et al., 2023).

According to the results, attitudes ($\beta_{A \gg D} = 0.227$, $t = 4.936$, $p < 0.000$), subjective norm ($\beta_{SN \gg D} = 0.127$, $t = 2.663$, $p < 0.008$), positive anticipated emotions ($\beta_{PAE \gg D} = 0.127$, $t = 2.663$, $p < 0.008$), perceived behaviour control ($\beta_{PBC \gg D} = 0.328$, $t = 6.825$, $p < 0.000$) and frequency past behaviour ($\beta_{FPB \gg D} = 0.100$, $t = 2.965$, $p < 0.007$) positively and significantly affect desire, while negative anticipated emotions ($\beta_{NAE \gg D} = 0.067$, $t = 1.404$, $p > 0.161$) do not significantly affect desire. Thus, hypotheses H₁, H₂, H₃, H₇ and H₉ are supported, and hypothesis H₄ is not supported. Desire ($\beta_{D \gg I} = 0.219$, $t = 4.420$, $p < 0.000$) and frequency past behaviour ($\beta_{FPB \gg I} = 0.252$, $t = 4.423$, $p < 0.000$) have a significant positive effect on intentions. Therefore, H₅ and H₁₀ hypotheses are supported. Intentions ($\beta_{I \gg B} = 0.195$, $t = 4.195$, $p < 0.000$), perceived behaviour control ($\beta_{PBC \gg B} = 0.142$, $t = 3.244$, $p < 0.001$), frequency past behaviour ($\beta_{FPB \gg B} = 0.196$, $t = 3.489$, $p < 0.001$), frequency past behaviour ($\beta_{FPB \gg B} = 0.196$, $t = 3.489$, $p < 0.001$), lionization ($\beta_{L \gg B} = 0.196$, $t = 3.489$, $p < 0.001$), and opposition ($\beta_{O \gg B} = 0.196$, $t = 3.489$, $p < 0.001$) have a significant positive effect on behaviour, whereas communalization ($\beta_{C \gg B} = 0.196$, $t = 3.489$, $p < 0.001$) has a significant effect. Therefore, hypotheses H₆, H₈, H₁₁, H₁₂ and H₁₃ are supported, while hypothesis H₁₄ is not supported (see Table 6 and Figure 2).

Figure 2. Results of the research model

Source: Authors' calculations

5. Conclusion and Implications

In conclusion, the results of this study support the idea that locavorism has a significant impact on the behavioral intentions of tourists participating in the Alaçatı Herb Festival in İzmir province. The findings indicate that attitudes, subjective norms, positive anticipated emotions, perceived behavioral control, and frequency of past behavior have a positive and significant effect on desire, which, in turn, positively impacts intentions. The results also suggest that promoting the benefits of local food and products, such as their unique taste, supporting local farmers and businesses, and preserving local culture and heritage, can positively influence the desire and intention to consume local food and products.

The study sheds light on the significant role of locavorism in influencing tourists' behavioral intentions, highlighting the importance of promoting and encouraging the consumption of local food and products among travelers. These findings provide valuable insights for various stakeholders, including local governments and tourism organizations, who can use them to formulate effective strategies and initiatives that enhance the overall tourist experience. By making local food and products more visible and appealing, tourists can be motivated to incorporate these experiences into their travels, supporting local businesses and preserving local culture and heritage.

The theoretical implications of this study are noteworthy, contributing to a better understanding of how locavorism shapes tourists' intentions toward local food and products. The study demonstrates the applicability of GDB (the theory that attitudes influence behavior, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, and intentions) in the context of locavorism. By highlighting the significant impact of GDB variables on tourists' behavioral intentions toward local food and products, this research adds to the existing literature. It demonstrates the relevance of GDB theory in the context of promoting local consumption. The study highlights the importance of positive attitudes and perceived behavioral control in influencing tourists' intentions to support local food and products. Policymakers and practitioners can use this knowledge to develop strategies that foster positive attitudes and empower tourists to choose local options, thereby increasing local consumption.

The practical implications of this study are multifaceted and provide valuable insights for different stakeholders to promote local food and products effectively. Fostering positive attitudes, creating social pressure to choose local options, increasing perceived behavioral control, and incentivizing past behavior related to local consumption can all positively influence tourists' desire to engage with local products. Local governments and tourism organizations can capitalize on these findings by designing marketing campaigns highlighting local foods and

products' unique characteristics and benefits, including their distinctive flavors, regional significance, and cultural heritage. In addition, by improving accessibility and availability, authorities can make it easier for tourists to incorporate local experiences into their travel plans. Implementing loyalty programs or offering incentives for repeat local consumption can also be beneficial in cultivating a culture of supporting local businesses.

Limitations and Recommendations for Future Research

As with any research endeavor, this study has limitations that should be considered when interpreting the results. The research was conducted specifically at the Alaçatı Herb Festival in İzmir province, and as such, the findings may not be readily applicable to other tourist destinations or cultural events. To gain a broader understanding, it is essential to conduct further research to explore the effects of locavorism in different contexts and to assess the generalizability of the findings. The study was structured as cross-sectional, meaning it cannot establish causality. To establish cause-and-effect relationships, future studies could use longitudinal or experimental methodologies to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship more conclusively between locavorism and tourists' behavioral intentions toward local food and products. It is important to acknowledge that the study relied on self-reported data, which may be susceptible to social desirability bias. To increase the validity of future research, it may be prudent to include objective measures, such as purchase records or food diaries, to verify findings.

The present study primarily focused on investigating the impact of locavorism on tourists' behavioral intentions toward local food and products. However, additional research is needed to explore tourists' actual behavior and evaluate the effectiveness of initiatives aimed at promoting local food and products under the influence of locavorism. Given the limitations identified in this study, further research is warranted to obtain a more comprehensive and well-rounded understanding of the relationship between locavorism and tourists' behavioral intentions toward local food and products. Addressing these limitations in future research using longitudinal or experimental designs, objective measures, and delving into actual behavior will help shed more light on this topic.

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